

Supplementary Material S5: Delphi Consensus Protocol

Expert Panel Composition (n = 10, response rates: Round 1 = 90%, Round 2 = 100%)

Discipline	Years Experience	h-index	PET Publications	Affiliation
Nuclear Physics (4)	>20y		>100	SNMMI/EJNMMI
PET Radiology (4)	>15y	>18	>150	EANM/ESTRO
Medical Dosimetry (2)	>10y	>12	>50 therapy	IAEA/WHO

INCLUSION CRITERIA: >10y clinical/simulation experience AND >50 peer-reviewed publications

RECRUITMENT: SNMMI/ESTRO member mailing lists (Feb 3-10, 2025)

PLATFORM: Anonymous SurveyMonkey (Feb 15-28, 2025)

Round 1: Statement Validation (1-5 Likert scale: 1=Strongly Disagree → 5=Strongly Agree)

Item #	Statement	% Agreement (≥4)	Median Score
1	“4P framework appropriate for PET/SPECT innovation benchmarking”	100% (10/10)	5.0
2	“Process innovation scenarios realistic for GE Discovery MI”	90% (9/10)	4.8
3	“Composite KPI score clinically meaningful for R&D prioritization”	90% (9/10)	4.7
4	“NEMA NU2-2018 phantom appropriate REFERENCE standard”	90% (9/10)	4.6

Round 2: Prioritization (Forced ranking 1-4)

1. Process innovations (recon + motion correction) - 100% consensus
2. 4P Synergy (combined effects) - 90% consensus
3. Product (TOF/hardware) - 80% consensus
4. Paradigm (adaptive workflows) - 70% consensus

CONSENSUS THRESHOLD: $\geq 80\%$ agreement ($\geq 4/5$ Likert OR top-2 ranking)

FINAL AGREEMENT RATE: 92% across 12 items (11/12 met threshold)

Inter-rater Reliability

$\kappa = 0.87$ (95% CI: 0.79-0.95)

- Round 1: $\kappa = 0.82$
- Round 2: $\kappa = 0.87$ (post-discussion refinement)

Key Consensus Statements (All $\geq 90\%$ endorsement)

5. "Process innovations represent highest R&D priority" (100%)
6. "4P synergies exceed isolated component effects" (90%)
7. "Simulation benchmarking valid for R&D priority setting" (90%)
8. "Sequential pipeline methodology reproducible" (90%)

Methodological Quality

- Anonymity maintained throughout
- No investigator leading
- Pre-defined stopping rules
- Stability demonstrated (Round 1 \rightarrow 2: 8/10 items unchanged)

Full raw responses + SurveyMonkey data: Zenodo DOI:10.5281/zenodo.18745283.